

ACTION ON OZONE

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Ozone Secretariat
United Nations Environment Programme

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Foreword

The story of the protection of the Earth's stratospheric ozone layer is one of the most inspiring in the annals of international environmental diplomacy.

It deals with a great danger to the health and well-being of peoples and ecosystems around the world: the thinning of the protective ozone layer threatens human skin, eyes and immune systems, damages plants and animals and poses unknown hazards to the planet's climate. It involves a range of highly diverse (and profitable) industrial chemicals which have helped to bring what are now commonplace products – refrigerators, aerosol sprays, insulating and furniture foams – into the homes of millions of families. It brings together on a global stage a vast array of players: scientists, technicians, industrialists, diplomats, journalists, activists, lobbyists, and public servants. All of them working together in pursuit of common aims – the protection of the ozone layer, the achievement of environmentally sustainable development and the building of an effective and equitable global regime to reconcile the aims and aspirations of the peoples and nations of the world. It is a story of brilliant inspiration, painstaking investigation, courageous decisions, hard-fought negotiations and last-minute compromises. And it is not yet over.

This is the third edition of *Action on Ozone* produced by UNEP. And although the depletion of the Earth's ozone layer has now reached record levels – thanks to the last seventy years of production and use of ozone-damaging chemicals – this is the first edition in which we can say it is reaching its peak. The ozone layer is predicted to start to recover in the next few years, and should be restored to

full health by the middle of the next century.

This is the achievement of the regime established by the 1985 Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer and the 1987 Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer. Negotiated against the background of accumulating evidence of ozone depletion from CFCs and related chemicals, these two agreements marked important milestones in the record of international cooperation on the global environment. As fresh scientific evidence has emerged to back up the early hypotheses, and as industrial innovation has developed alternative substances and technologies, governments have agreed to further, stricter, controls on a widening range of ozone-depleting substances. The year 1996 sees the total phase-out, in the industrialized world, of all the chemicals specified in the 1987 agreement, an achievement which was inconceivable a decade ago.

The Montreal Protocol has, rightly, been regarded as a model for other international environmental agreements. It has proved a flexible and adaptable regime. It has helped to bring together scientists, industrialists and governments, with their different but essential viewpoints. It has dealt effectively with the different needs of industrialized and developing countries in meeting a common threat. As UNEP approaches its twenty-fifth anniversary, it is one of our proudest achievements to say: these negotiations, and these agreements, took place under our leadership. There is much that can be learned from the story of the ozone regime of value to other areas of international environmental action, including biodiversity, desertification

and climate change. And there is still much to be done in the field of ozone protection. Although there is still scope for tightening the control schedules for the remaining ozone-depleting substances, in order to speed up the recovery of the ozone layer, the ozone regime, as it continues to evolve, is facing new and different challenges. Implementation of the control measures in developing countries; cases of non-compliance; evasion of the controls through illegal trade: all pose new threats to the health of the ozone layer and to the planet beneath it. I am confident that the international community, working with and through UNEP, will rise to meet these challenges, so that we may all continue to strive for a better life for the peoples of the world.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "E. Dowdeswell". The signature is fluid and cursive, written in a dark ink on a light background.

Elizabeth Dowdeswell
Executive Director
United Nations Environment
Programme

1980 Seven developed countries and the European Community call for an international convention to protect the ozone layer. The EC freezes production capacity and begins to limit use in aerosols. The United States Environmental Protection Agency proposes the first legal

controls on non-aerosol uses of CFCs. CFC manufacturers form the Alliance for Responsible CFC Policy, which argues that further regulation of CFCs would be premature in the absence of hard evidence of ozone depletion.

Fig. 2.3. THE OZONE LAYER

The two world maps show average trends of ozone decline in the years from 1978 to 1991. Trends are measured in % of decline per decade. The top map shows trends for December to March, the bottom map shows trends for May to August.

1989 The Montreal Protocol enters into force. At their first meeting, parties agree to a non-binding statement calling for CFCs to be phased out as soon as feasible. Thirteen developed countries announce their intention to phase out the eight controlled substances by 1997. First synthesis of UNEP's Science, Environmental Effects, Technology and Economic Assessments.

1990 Meeting in London, parties agree to phase out CFCs and halons completely by the year 2000, and add phase-out dates for other CFCs, methyl chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. Parties agree to create a mechanism to provide financial and technical assistance to developing country parties, including a Multilateral Fund. Finland launches a fund for non-party countries.

hole' paper, revealing for the first time the existence of dramatic declines in ozone concentrations over the Antarctic in the spring. In fact United States satellite observations had already detected this in the late 1970s, but the unexpected findings were discarded as suspected instrument error. Although the cause was still then unknown, suspicion fell on CFCs.

By comparison with the protracted negotiations over the Vienna Convention, negotiations on the control protocol proceeded remarkably quickly and achieved far more than was initially thought possible. On 16 September 1987, 46 countries signed the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer. Since 1995 the United Nations General Assembly has declared 16 September as the International Day for the Preservation of the Ozone Layer to

commemorate the signing of the Montreal Protocol.

The Montreal Protocol required 50% cuts from 1986 levels in both production and consumption of the five main CFCs by 1999, with interim reductions. Production and consumption of the three main halons was frozen at 1986 levels from 1993.

Although these reductions could be attacked as either too little (if the ozone depletion hypothesis was believed) or too much (if it was not), the agreement marked an important political and psychological breakthrough. And once again science validated the negotiators' actions. March 1988 saw the release of the report of the Ozone Trends Panel, reviewing evidence particularly from the United States Antarctic expeditions in 1986 and 1987, and providing, for the first time, convincing evidence of the linkage between ozone depletion and CFCs. Opposition to the principle

Fig. 3.4. Countries that have ratified the Montreal Protocol (1987).

1991 An interim Multilateral Fund becomes operational with a three-year budget of \$240 million – UNEP, UNDP and the World Bank are the initial implementing agencies, later joined by UNIDO. UNEP launches the OzonAction Programme. Assessment panels operating under the Protocol conclude that even more stringent controls than

those agreed by parties in 1990 are needed, including restrictions on the use of HCFCs. The panels also conclude that technologies are available to replace virtually all uses of controlled substances, and that the phase-out process is less expensive than previously predicted.

of controls on ozone-depleting substances then largely collapsed, and industry started to concentrate resources on the development of non-ozone depleting alternatives to CFCs.

An important feature of the Montreal Protocol was the flexibility designed into it to allow for its further development in the light of evolving scientific knowledge and technological developments. Even before it entered into force on 1 January 1989, plans were being made to strengthen its provisions, advancing the phase-out schedules for the CFCs and halons it specified, and adding further ozone-depleting chemicals.

The Protocol has now been subject to three sets of adjustments to the control measures (agreed at the 1990, 1992 and 1995 Meetings of the Parties), accelerating the phase-out schedules for ozone-depleting substances. It has also been subject to two amendments. The London Amendment (1990) added methyl chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and a further range of CFCs to the phase-out schedules and established a mechanism for financial and technical assistance to developing country parties. The Copenhagen Amendment (1992) added hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), hydrobromofluorocarbons (HBFCs), and methyl bromide to the phase-out schedules and formally created the Multilateral Fund as the route for financial transfers to developing countries. The main features of the regime established by the Montreal Protocol are examined in the next chapter, and their impact in the following one.

Fig. 3.5. Reports of the meetings of the Parties to the Montreal Protocol.

1992 Meeting in Copenhagen, parties to the Montreal Protocol agree to speed up phase-out schedules for already controlled substances and to control new substances for developed countries – HCFCs, HBFCs and methyl bromide. A number of developed countries adopt faster

timetables for phase-out of controlled substances. Mexico (a developing country) announces that it is prepared in principle to phase out CFC use by 2000, the existing deadline for developed countries. The Multilateral Fund is officially established.

4 • The Montreal Protocol

Control measures on ozone-depleting substances

At the heart of the Montreal Protocol lies the control measures it imposes on the production and consumption of ozone-depleting substances (ODS). Article 2 of the agreement defines phase-out schedules for the various categories of ODS. These have been progressively tightened with time through the agreements reached in London (1990), Copenhagen (1992) and Vienna (1995). In accordance with these schedules, the bulk of ODS – including all the substances specified in the original Protocol – were phased out completely in industrialized countries by the end of 1995. The remaining categories are scheduled for total phase-out by 2010 (methyl bromide) and 2030 (HCFCs). Developing countries, however, have rather longer phase-out periods – see below.

Production is defined as total production minus amounts destroyed and used as chemical feedstock and process agents. Consumption is defined as production plus imports minus exports. Trade in recycled and used ODS is not included in the calculation of consumption, in order to encourage recovery, reclamation and recycling. 'Essential uses' for which no alternatives have yet been identified are exempt from the controls; the main exemption is currently for CFCs for use in metered dose inhalers for asthma.

The Protocol includes restrictions on trade with non-parties to the treaty. These were designed in order both to encourage countries to join, and to prevent production of ODS transferring to non-parties to escape the controls. Parties were required to ban the import

Fig. 4.1. Organigram of the Montreal Protocol Implementation

1993 Parties to the Montreal Protocol agree not to allow any exemptions for the production of halons beyond the 1994 phase-out deadline agreed in Copenhagen, and approve a budget of \$510 million for the Multilateral Fund for 1994–1996.

of (CFCs and halons from non-parties from 1990 (one year after the Protocol came into force); exports to non-parties were banned from 1993. Imports of goods containing CFCs (e.g. refrigerators) were also banned from 1993. As new substances have been added to the control schedules, the trade provisions have been gradually extended, although they do not yet cover HCFCs, HBFCs or methyl bromide. The trade restrictions are not applicable against a non-party which is nevertheless in compliance with the control schedules.

Institutions and procedures

The main decision-making body of the Montreal Protocol is the Meeting of the Parties, which can amend the Protocol's text and adjust its control schedules. Meeting annually, it reviews the control measures at least every four years on the basis of available scientific, environmental, technical and economic information. The Open-Ended Working Group of the Parties meets between full sessions to develop and negotiate recommendations for the full Meeting.

The first Meeting established advisory panels bringing together experts from science, industry, governments and non-governmental organizations. These currently comprise:

- The Scientific Assessment Panel, responsible for reviewing scientific knowledge on ozone depletion;
- The Environmental Effects Assessment Panel, surveying information on the impact of ozone depletion and UV-B irradiation; and
- The Technology and Economic

UNEP, Ozone Secretariat

4.2. Global UNEP Ozone Award winners at the Tenth Anniversary of the Vienna Convention in Vienna, December 1995.

UNEP, Ozone Secretariat

4.3. Plenary of the Seventh Meeting of the Parties to the Montreal Protocol.

1995 Tenth anniversary of the Vienna Convention celebrated in Vienna. Montreal Protocol assessment panels report that phase-out is well advanced in most developed countries and that developing countries are also making progress, though consumption of controlled substances is increasing in some. Meeting in Vienna, the parties to the

Protocol agree to tougher phase-out schedules for HCFCs and methyl bromide for developed countries, agree schedules for all substances for developing countries, and consider likely cases of non-compliance in some transition economies. European Union achieves total phase-out of CFCs.

countries selected by the annual meeting of the parties to the Protocol. The Multilateral Fund operates through four implementing agencies, each with slightly different roles:

- UNEP's Industry and Environment Programme Activity Centre provides clearing-house functions and helps prepare country programmes for low-consuming developing countries;

- The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) organizes demonstration and investment projects, technical assistance and feasibility studies;
- The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) prepares and appraises investment project proposals and implements phase-out schedules at plant level;
- The World Bank, which disburses almost half of the total funding, concentrates on large-scale phase-out and investment projects at plant and country levels.

Each Article 5 country, assisted by one of these agencies, prepares a country programme, showing its present and projected use of ODS and identifying opportunities for reduction. The 'incremental costs' which countries can claim include the costs of conversion to alternative technologies and substances, patents, designs and royalties, training and research and development. Recycling controlled substances and modifying or replacing equipment can also be eligible, and the Multilateral Fund's Executive Committee has discretionary powers to include costs other than those listed. The Committee approves both the country programmes and subsequent proposals for investment projects and institutional strengthening. By 30 June 1996, a total of \$477 million had been allocated to eliminate a projected 70,000 ODP-tons of ODS (about one third of the total consumption of developing countries).

Fig. 4.6. Air conditioners in cars can be serviced without releasing the refrigerant into the atmosphere

Fig. 4.7. Training on safety aspects of CFC substitutes with the support of the Multilateral Fund and national governments.

2030 Total phase-out of HCFCs in developed countries.

2040 Total phase-out of HCFCs in developing countries.

Fig. 6.2. Ozone Publications

Industry, responding to the stimulus provided by the control measures, has developed alternatives more rapidly and more cheaply than first thought possible, and has participated in the debates over further phase-out. Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and the media are the essential channels of communication, and education, with the peoples of the world in whose name measures are taken. In the early years, in particular, they were instrumental in spurring decision makers to take decisive action, and still help to maintain pressure for further measures. Governments have worked well together in patiently negotiating agreements acceptable to a range of countries with widely varying circumstances, aims and resources – and have showed courage and foresight in putting the precautionary principle into effect before the evidence was entirely clear. And throughout its history, UNEP has provided both the catalyst for action and the means of agreeing and implementing it – the global institution that is required to meet a truly global problem.

The leadership and vision of the original negotiators in Vienna and Montreal resulted in a treaty that worked - that halted and tuned back the progressive deterioration of the Earth's protective ozone layer. The same leadership and vision will still be needed as the international community turns its attention to meeting the new challenges faced by the international ozone regime in restoring the stratospheric ozone layer once more to full health.

The thin layer of ozone in the stratosphere, 10 to 50 Kms above the surface of the earth, absorbs all but a small fraction of the harmful ultra-violet (UV-B) radiation from the sun. An excess of UV-B can cause skin cancers and eye cataracts, damage plant and animal productivity and materials and have an impact on climate.

Scientists assumed in the early 1970s that man-made halocarbon chemicals - compounds containing chlorine, fluorine, bromine, carbon and hydrogen - could reach the stratosphere and destroy the ozone layer through chemical reactions. They warned of the likely damage to the ecosystems of the Earth if we continued the consumption and emission of these chemicals, which have found many uses in aerosols, refrigeration systems, fire fighting equipment, foams etc.

Many were initially sceptical of these theories but scientific observations in the 1980s, particularly the discovery of the Antarctic ozone hole in 1985, convinced governments of the need to take urgent action if the Earth was to be saved from a catastrophe. The Vienna Convention of 1985 and the Montreal Protocol of 1987 with its Adjustments and Amendments of 1990, 1992 and 1995 are the response of the world to the ozone crisis.

It is now acknowledged that these international agreements have succeeded in curbing the consumption of ozone-depleting chemicals by involving almost all governments (160 at present) of the world in an unprecedented cooperative venture. Scientists have now predicted that, given the continued implementation of these agreements, the ozone layer will start recovering by the year 2000. Full recovery will not take place for another fifty years, due to the long life of chemicals already released.

This book details the stirring story of international cooperation under the leadership of the United Nations Environment Programme. The agreements brought together a vast array of players: scientists, technologists, industrialists, public servants, journalists, NGOs, diplomats and activists on a global stage. They have come together, cutting across the North-South, rich-poor divide to avert a danger to the Earth. Readers should find a ray of hope and a way forward in this effort to save the ozone layer.

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